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Urban Waste Produced in the Italian Regions

They decreased on average by 7.6% between 2010 and 2021

Istat calculates the value of urban waste produced in the Italian regions. The data is available in the period between 2010 and 2021 in the Italian regions.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of urban waste produced in 2022. Emilia Romagna is in first place by value of urban waste produced in 2021 with a value of 641 units, followed by Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 600 units and from Tuscany with an amount of 598 units. In the middle of the table are Friuli Venezia Giulia with a value of 501 units, followed by Piedmont with a value of 500 units and Veneto with a value of 487 units. Calabria closes the ranking with a value of 408 units, followed by Molise with a value of 383 units and Basilicata with a value of 356 units. On average, the Italian regions produced a value of urban waste equal to 494.25 in 2022.

Ranking of the Italian regions by change in the value of urban waste between 2010 and 2021. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place for change in the value of urban waste between 2010 and 2021 with a corresponding amount of +1.81% to a variation from an amount of 496 units up to a value of 505 units. Friuli Venezia Giulia follows with a growth in urban waste produced corresponding to a value of +0.8% or from an amount of 497 units up to a value of 501 units. In third place Campania with a reduction in the percentage value of urban waste corresponding to an amount of -1.26% or from a value of 478 units up to a value of 472 units. In the middle of the table we find Lombardy with a value equal to -6.07% corresponding to a reduction from an amount of 511 units up to a value of 480 units. Basilicata follows with a variation corresponding to -6.56% or from a value of 381 units up to a value of 356 units. Emilia Romagna follows with a reduction corresponding to a value of -6.97% corresponding to a variation from 689 units up to a value of 641 units. Calabria closes the ranking with a reduction equal to an amount of -13.92% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 474 units up to a value of 408 units. Umbria follows with a variation corresponding to -15.25% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 610 units up to a value of 517 units. Lazio closes the ranking with a reduction in waste produced corresponding to a reduction of -17.92% equal to a reduction from an amount of 614 units up to a value of 504 units. Between 2010 and 2021 the value of urban waste produced decreased on average by an amount equal to 7.6% or from an amount of 535 to a value of 494 units.

Urban waste produced in the Italian macro-regions between 2010 and 2021. The value of urban waste produced decreased in all Italian macro-regions between 2010 and 2021. Specifically, this value decreased in the North by an amount equal to -4.80%, in the North-West for an amount of -5.93%, North-East with a value equal to -3.35%, Center with a value equal to -13.94%, Southern Italy with a variation equal to -7.85%, South with -6.75%, and Islands with a value equal to -9.57%. Therefore, although the Southern regions have a level of urban waste production that is certainly lower than the

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level of the Central and Northern regions, it follows that the value of this variable has decreased in all Italian macro-regions.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized for the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Four clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Lombardy, Abruzzo, Veneto, Piedmont, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Sicily, Puglia, Sardinia, Trentino Alto Adige, Campania;
- Cluster 2: Emilia Romagna, Tuscany, Valle d'Aosta;
- Cluster 3: Molise, Basilicata, Calabria;
- Cluster 4: Lazio, Umbria, Liguria, Marche.

From the metric point of view we can note the presence of the following system $C2 > C4 > C1 > C3$. From the clustering we can see that the central regions tend to be characterized by high levels of urban waste production. While the regions of the North and South, with the exception of Emilia Romagna and Valle d'Aosta, tend to have lower levels of urban waste production than the regions of Central Italy.

Conclusions. The value of urban waste production has decreased in all Italian regions and macro-regions. The Central regions tend to be characterized by high levels of urban waste production together with Emilia Romagna and Valle d'Aosta. Apparently there are no socio-economic reasons that could justify the fact that in some regions there is a very high level of urban waste production compared to others. Perhaps the only exception could be made for Lazio since it hosts the most populous city in Italy and therefore it could have a greater production of urban waste. Similar considerations can be made for example for Emilia Romagna which is characterized by a dense network of fairly populated cities. However, it is difficult to identify a reason for the high levels of urban waste production in the Aosta Valley, since it is a sparsely populated region with urban centers that are absolutely negligible from a strictly demographic point of view. It follows that it is very likely that the production of urban waste is mainly due to behavioral and cultural issues rather than to economic-social motivations. However, it is certainly a positive fact that the value of urban waste production decreased in all Italian macro-regions between 2010 and 2021. In this sense, a positive role could have been played both by separate waste collection and by the change in orientation of the population increasingly sensitive to environmental issues and the circular economy.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

